

SOME EFFECTIVE WAYS OF READING NEWSPAPER ARTICLES**Barno Mukhtorova***teacher, PhD student, FerSU***Mokhlaroyim Kayumova***4th year student, FerSU*

Abstract. This article highlights some challenges in reading newspaper articles and suggests some tips for effective reading articles. Reading newspaper articles is discussed as a skill that makes other skills such as critical skills, improving vocabulary and language skills and cultural awareness develop. Besides, the given article provides some benefits of reading newspaper articles that can be used to develop a general reading habit.

Keywords: newspaper article, critical thinking skills, skimming.

Аннотация. В этой статье освещаются некоторые проблемы, связанные с чтением газетных статей, и предлагаются некоторые советы по эффективному чтению статей. Чтение газетных статей обсуждается как навык, который способствует развитию других навыков, таких как критические навыки, улучшение словарного запаса, языковых навыков и культурной осведомленности. Кроме того, данная статья дает некоторые преимущества чтения газетных статей, которые можно использовать для выработки общей привычки к чтению.

Ключевые слова: газетная статья, навыки критического мышления, беглый просмотр текста (скимминг)

Introduction.

Reading newspaper articles is an important activity that provides individuals with knowledge about current events, cultural perspectives, and different opinions. Newspapers have a rich history that dates back to the 17th century and have evolved to become a primary source of information for millions of people worldwide. From the first handwritten news bulletins to modern online news platforms, newspapers

have evolved to become an indispensable source of information and knowledge. This article will explore the importance of reading newspaper articles and how to make the most of this valuable activity.

Benefits of reading newspaper articles.

Staying informed about current events: Reading newspaper articles allows individuals to stay informed about local, national, and international events. This helps individuals understand how events are connected and how they affect their lives.

Learning about different perspectives and opinions: Newspapers offer a range of opinions and perspectives on a variety of topics, giving readers a chance to broaden their horizons and learn about issues from different viewpoints.

Developing critical thinking skills: Reading newspaper articles helps readers develop their critical thinking skills by analyzing the information presented and assessing its credibility and relevance.

Improving vocabulary and language skills: Regular reading of newspapers can improve one's vocabulary and language skills, which can be beneficial in academic and professional settings.

Enhancing cultural awareness: Newspapers offer readers an opportunity to learn about different cultures and lifestyles, which can increase their cultural awareness and understanding.

Tips for effective reading of newspaper articles

Choosing the right newspaper and section for your interests: Readers should choose newspapers that align with their interests and offer relevant sections on topics they care about.

Skimming headlines and summaries to determine relevance: Skimming headlines and summaries can help readers quickly determine the relevance of an article and decide whether to read it further.

Reading the entire article carefully: It is important to read the entire article carefully to fully understand the topic and the author's viewpoint.

Taking notes and highlighting important points: Taking notes and highlighting important points can help readers remember and analyze the information presented in an article.

Reflecting on the information and considering multiple perspectives: After reading an article, readers should reflect on the information presented and consider different perspectives to broaden their understanding of the topic.

Common challenges when reading newspaper articles

Overwhelming amount of information: With the abundance of information available in newspapers, readers may feel overwhelmed and find it difficult to keep up with everything.

Biases and inaccuracies in reporting: Some newspapers may have biases or inaccuracies in their reporting, which can affect readers' understanding and interpretation of the news.

Time constraints and busy schedules: Busy schedules and time constraints may make it difficult for individuals to read newspapers regularly and stay informed about current events.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, reading newspaper articles has numerous benefits that can enhance an individual's knowledge, critical thinking skills, and cultural awareness. By following the tips provided, readers can effectively navigate the challenges and make the most of their newspaper reading experience. To make the most of reading newspaper articles, it's essential to choose the right newspaper and section for your interests. Making a regular habit of reading newspapers can have a positive impact on one's personal and professional life.

REFERENCES:

1. Dubrovsky, V. J., & Warrington, P. (2013). Media use and its effects on satisfaction with democracy in the United States. *Journal of Media and Communication Studies*, 5(8), 126-137.
2. Grier, S. A., & Brummett, B. H. (2010). The positive effects of newspaper reading

- ng on interpersonal closeness and psychological well-being: An exploration using the daily diary method. *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 87(3-4), 668-685.
3. Hirsh-Pasek, K., & Golinkoff, R. M. (2016). *Becoming brilliant: What science tells us about raising successful children*. American Psychological Association.
 4. Liao, Y. W. (2016). A study of newspaper reading habits and academic performance of high school students. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(20), 147-154.
 5. Rose, C., & Glass, S. (2018). The role of newspapers in building civil society. *Journalism*, 19(1), 90-106.
 6. qizi Usmonova, U. H., & Mukhtorova, B. (2023). PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS OF LANGUAGE. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(1), 241-244.
 7. Абдуразакова, Ш., & Мухторова, Б. (2023). ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕКСТА. *Scientific progress*, 4(1), 369-373.
 8. Mukhtorova, B. (2023). THE LINGUISTIC AND CONCEPTUAL PICTURE OF THE WORLD. *Science and innovation*, 2(B1), 461-466.
 9. Мухторова, Б. А. (2022, September). МОДАЛЛИК КАТЕГОРИЯСИНИНГ ЛИСОНИЙ ҲАМДА МАНТИҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚИ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE "THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 55-61).
 10. Makhmudova, N. R. (2019). The use of multimedia learning tools in the English language. *Мировая наука*, (9), 44-48.
 11. Abbasova, N. K. (2018). Using Effective Techniques Developing Learners' Critical Thinking in Teaching English Proverbs and Sayings. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (6).
 12. Makhmudova, N. (2022). PRAGMATIC SIGNS OF ORNITHONYMS IN PROVERBS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(2), 88-91.
 13. Makhmudova, N. (2021). BIRD NAMES REALLY MATTER: FEATURES OF ORNITHONYMES IN LANGUAGE. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 116-118.
 14. Makhmudova, N. (2021). LEXICAL-SEMANTIC GROUP OF ORNITHONYMS IN LANGUAGE AND THEIR USE. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(5), 107-116.